

USAGE OF SUBJECT GATEWAYS ON WEB RESOURCES AMONG RESEARCH SCHOLARS IN BHARATHIYAR UNIVERSITY- A STUDY

M. Sakthi Suganth* & M. Packiyaraj**

* Librarian, Nachimuthu Polytechnic College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Librarian, R.M.K. College of Engineering and Technology, Thiruvallur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Sakthi Suganth & M. Packiyaraj, "Usage of Subject Gateways on

Web Resources among Research Scholars in Bharathiyar University- A Study", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 264-267, 2016

Abstract:

Almost user has quick and specific information to their researches for studies. For this purposes subject wise gateways are role is very important. It is also used to library professionals. This paper aims at the usage of subject gateways on web resources among research scholars in Bharathiyar University for explore knowledge to researchers, users, etc. it's available web recourses are life science world, BUL gateway, Academic info, Intute, About, Dmoz, Infomine, Librarian Internet Index, Scout Report, Virtual Library and other Archives. This paper compare several differences with other subject information gateway systems, such as embody scope, resource types, organization system, resource description, retrieval function, appreciation service, renewal and maintenance, cooperation model ,amount of data etc. For the more, the paper put forward some good ideas of developing Subject Gateway system

Introduction:

Internet and its most used component WWW has turned into a biggest source of information with widest coverage and the fastest access. It is the most powerful tool for global communication and exchange of information. Koch, Golub and Ardo (2006) in their study explore the navigation behavior of all users of a large web service, Renardus, using web log analysis. Renardus provides integrated searching and browsing access to quality-controlled web resources from major individual subject gateway services. The main navigation feature is subject browsing through the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) based on mapping of classes of resources from the distributed gateways to the DDC structure.

Resources Developments at Bharathiyar University:

The Bharathiyar University was established at Coimbatore by the Government of Tamilnadu in February, 1982 under the provision of the Bharathiyar University Act, 1981 (Act 1 of 1982). The Postgraduate Centre of the University of Madras, which was functioning in Coimbatore before 1982 formed the core of the Bharathiyar University. In May, 1985 the University received the recognition from University Grants Commission (UGC) New Delhi for the purpose of grants. The University named after the great national poet Subramania Bharathi is enshrined with the motto "Educate to Elevate". In the University, every effort is harnessed to realize his dream of making educational institutions as temple of learning. It is the aim of the University to participate in the task of inculcating necessary Knowledge, Skills and Creative Attitudes and values among the youth of the country to contribute more effectively towards establishing an equitable social and economic and secular ideal of our nation. The Library of Bharathiyar University was established in the year 1981 at the Madras University Autonomous Postgraduate Centre of the University is an area of 11,750 sq.feet. The seating capacity currently is about 300, and has over 1,47,350 volumes covering all disciplines. The library subscribes to 153 National and International journals and seven leading news papers. 150 journals magazines and periodicals are received on gratis. Back issues of journals are available some dating back to 1880's. Photocopying facility is also available inside the library.

Objectives:

This paper is to explore the usage of subject gateways on web resources among 360 research scholars in Bharathiyar University, Coimbatore

- To identify awareness of the web and web resources
- Usage of subject gateways on web resources by the research scholars
- To find out Purposes for using web resources
- To discover problems faced by the researchers
- To find user satisfaction on web resources
- To suggest ways to improve the web resources on subject gateways

Review of Literature:

Zeeman and Turner (2006) in their paper has discussed that Library and Archives Canada (LAC) has capitalized on the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) potential for organizing Web resources in two projects. Since 1995, LAC has been providing a service that offers links to authoritative Web resources about Canada categorized according to the DDC via its Web site. More recently, LAC has partnered with the federal government Department of Canadian Heritage to manage Web content related to Canadian culture in a DDC-based subject tree. Although the DDC works well to organize a broadly-based collection, challenges have been

encountered in adapting it for a specific subject domain. Schroeder (2001) in her article have talked about Dewey Decimal Classification-22nd edition and described various DDC web resources

Saupel (2010) in the article has mentioned that social tagging systems, known as "folksonomies," represent an important part of web resource discovery as they enable free and unrestricted browsing through information space. Folksonomies consisting of subject designators (tags) assigned by users, however, have one important drawback: they do not express semantic relationships, either hierarchical or associative, between tags. As a consequence, the use of tags to browse information resources requires moving from one resource to another, based on coincidence and not on the pre-established meaningful or logical connections that may exist between related resources. We suggest that the semantic structure of the Universal Decimal Classification (UDC) may be used in complementing and supporting tag-based browsing. In this work, two specific questions were investigated: 1) Are terms used as tags in folksonomies included in the UDC?; and, 2) Which facets of UDC match the characteristics of documents or information objects that are tagged in folksonomies? A collection of the most popular tags from Amazon, Library Thing, Delicious, and 43Things was investigated. The universal nature of UDC was examined through the universality of topics and facets covering diverse human interests which are at the same time interconnected and form a rich and intricate semantic structure. The results suggest that UDC-supported folksonomies could be implemented in resource discovery, in particular in library portals and catalogues

Methodology:

Data was collected using a questionnaire method. The collection covers only research scholars. There are several departments in the University, of which questionnaires were distributed to departments of Tamil, Commerce, LIS, Computer science and more...

A total of 160 questionnaires were distributed in meeting point. A total of 155 valid questionnaires were collected from research scholars. The response rate was 96%.

Data Analysis & interpretation:

Experience & Frequency:

The results in table show that research scholar's knowledge in web resources

Table 1: Awareness of Web resources

Academic Status	Frequency	Yes	No	Total
Research Scholar's	155	155	0	155
%	100	100	0	100

The majority of respondents had 2-4 years experience of accessing the web resources and basic known

Table 2: Research Scholar's Experience:-

Academic Status	Below 1 year	1-2 years	3-4 years	Above 4 years	Total
Research Scholar's	26	52	45	32	155
%	16.77	33.55	29.03	20.65	100

To access frequency of use, respondents were asked to indicate any of Daily, 2-3 times per week, Once a week, Fortnightly and Monthly wise.

Academic Status	Daily	2-3 times per week	Once a week	Fortnightly	Monthly	Total
Research Scholar's	6	15	42	75	17	155
%	3.87	9.68	27.1	48.39	10.97	100

Web Resources Purpose & Methods:

More than research scholar's using web resources purpose an almost equal number for education, communicating with others, publishing journal related and other entertainment.

Academic Status	Research	Communication	Journals	Entertainment	Total
Research Scholar's	102	34	12	7	155
%	65.81	21.94	7.74	4.52	100

More than research scholar's respondents use the web resources for searching, e-journals, E-Books, Database, Reports, ETDs, Reference and proceedings toBU library Website. In compare several differences with other subject information gateway systems, such as embody scope, resource types, organization system, resource description, retrieval function , appreciation service, renewal and maintenance, cooperation model ,amount of data etc. For the more, the paper put forward some good ideas of developing Subject Gateway system

Academic Status	Web Resources	BU Subject Gateways	Generals	Others	Total
Research Scholar's	72	42	15	26	155
%	46.45	27.1	9.68	16.77	100

More than research scholar's using methods in search engines, direct web address typing Internet gateways, BU Library website and other database

Academic Status	Search Engines	Direct web URL	Internet Gateways	Library website	Total
Research Scholar's	97	16	22	20	155
%	62.58	10.32	14.19	12.9	100

Usage of Subject Gateways:

Subject gateways may be identified in the usual ways in which any Internet resource may be found by use of a search engine or general directory, such as Google, from printed listings. With the increase in the number and value of these tools, specific listings of subject gateways are now being created: some libraries and information centers, which initially attempted to list useful Internet resources, have now moved to simply listing subject gateways. The BU library web page <https://www.b-u.ac.in/home/library> has been assigned subject gateways on web resources. The following category was analyzed in the form of subject gateways.

B U Subject Gateways

Subject Gateways Services:

There is no precise definition of a subject gateway. They share several characteristics for research scholars. They are, necessarily, subject specific, including resources pertaining to some restricted topic, and type of user. Unlike search engines, whose indexes are automatically constructed by software agents following automated identification of resources, gateway resources are selected intellectually by human experts. Explicit, and often strict, criteria are applied in the selection of resources, and the resources thus chosen are described and classified and/or indexed by the same human experts. Resources are selected on two general counts: appropriateness of subject content, and quality of the information resource. Appropriateness of subject coverage, or 'scope' of resource, is usually regarded as easier to assess than quality. The following services going in the form of BU Library website for average web resources to users.

Subject Gateways Services

Satisfaction:

70% of the research scholar's are fully satisfied with web resources and 30% of the user partially satisfied.

Academic Status	Fully	Partially	Minimum Satisfied	No Comment	Total
Research Scholar's	92	12	14	37	155
%	59.35	7.74	9.03	23.87	100

Finding & Conclusion:

- Research Scholar's have huge experience using web resources
- Wifi Campus and free internet access is provided by the BU University
- BU Digital Library for most comfortable place for accessing web resources
- Many E- resources available in University Library
- Subject Gateways Awareness need to research scholars
- Search engines are the most common way of web resources
- Downloading problems, advt., overload information, E – Waste management are the major problems faced by research scholars
- In Tamil Department faced problem by how to search information in Tamil letters

The usage of web resources is a major source of communication and information in present world. Libraries in India are fast transforming into digital libraries and virtual learning resource centers. It is important that BU University maintain the library web page with all necessary technology with subject gateways for the effective use of information in higher education and research. A large portion of user is aware about subject gateways, but they do not know all its techniques and applications. Further a few scholars the university still have no knowledge about the subject gateways web resources. They develop awareness and knowledge of the users.

References:

1. <http://159.226.100.135/ejournal/csdl-subjinfo.php>
2. <http://www.firstlight.cn>
3. <http://infomine.ucr.edu>
4. <http://www.intute.ac.uk>
5. Li Lili Comparative Study of International Architecture Information Gateway [Master dissertation]. Beijing : Chinese Academy of Agricultural Science, 2007
6. <http://navigation.calis.edu.cn/cm/allnotice.jsp>
7. Bavakutty, M., & Mohammed Salih, T.K. (1999). Internet services in Calicut University. In Kumar, P.S.G., & Vashisht, C.P. (Eds). Academic libraries in the Internet era. pp. 37-44. Ahmedabad: INFLIBNET.
8. Chandran, D. (2000). Use of Internet resources and services in S.V.University, Tirupathi environment. In Conference on information services in a networked environment in India (pp. 3.124-127), Organised by INFLIBNET, Ahmedabad, 18-20 December.
9. Jefferies, P., & Hussain, F. (1998). Using the Internet as a teaching resource. Education + Training 40 (8): 359-365
10. Kaur, A. (2000). Internet facility at Guru Nanak Dev University: A Survey. In XIX IASLIC Seminar proceeding (pp. 119-124). Bhopal: IASLIC.
11. Luambano, I., & Nawe, J. (2004). Internet use by students of the University of Dar E Salaam. Library Hi-Tech News 10: 13-17.
12. KR. Senthilkumar., Caliber 2009, Challenges to Preservation and Building Digital Libraries in India
13. <http://library.bu.ac.in/>
14. <https://sites.google.com/site/alagusenthil/>